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PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF TREATED AGGREGATES IN BITUMEN MIX DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Recycled Asphalt Pavement (RAP) is the largest recycled good in the United States and about 80 million tons are recycled yearly, saving taxpayers about \$1.5 million dollars. This paper explores the possibility of utilizing 100% of RAP materials in asphalt pavement. Asphalt mixtures are produced at 135⁰C in a typical plant. The main objective of the study is to determine the amount of effective binder available from RAP in the asphalt plant. The 100% RAP mixes have aged binder that can alter mix designs [1] and interaction with virgin binder. In this study, to determine low temperature cracking resistance and fatigue performance, samples were prepared using 100% Rap with no virgin binder and a 100% of RAP mix with virgin asphalt binder to achieve the optimum binder content of the mix. Second, to determine the effectiveness of binder from Rap materials, compaction test was performed by heating RAP materials [2] at various temperature. It was found that 100% of RAP mixes cannot be feasible for field use if an additional virgin binder is added to reach the optimum asphalt content. Based on limited test results, the low temperature grade was not within proper limits but the beam fatigue testing results were acceptable. Based on compaction test results, additional heating is needed to increase the effectiveness [3] of asphalt binders from RAP materials.

KEYWORDS:

Recycled Asphalt Pavement, optimum binder, Aggregate, Bitumen, Pavement Strength

INTRODUCTION

The most common method of rehabilitation for asphalt pavements involves the crushing of asphalt layers in distress before interference. This Procedure reproduces road compatibility, eliminates problems associated with cracking reflection, and maintains pavement geometry. Worldwide distributed maintenance technology generates a large amount of recovered asphalt as a product of the milling process. Although research management can also produce negligible production and surplus in mixed asphalt plants. In both cases, the bitumen binder and mineral complexes contained in the PR have important residual properties that should not be underestimated. Only on-site recycling can truly maximize the amount of recycle without compromising the mechanical properties of the final product while exploiting the intrinsic properties of RAP.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

CONSTITUENTS OF A MIX

The basic constituents materials used in mixture are [4]

- Coarse and fine aggregates
- Bitumen
- Rap

Coarse Aggregates

The aggregates that are retained on a 4.75mm sieve are referred to as a coarse aggregate

Fine Aggregates

The fine aggregates should be free from quarry dust and must be free of clay, silt, vegetation, or organic matter.

Fine aggregates are those which are passed from 4.75mm sieve and stored at 0.075mm.

Bituminous mix

The terms mainly adopted in the study “Bituminous Mix” are generally used only in engineering and construction documents which define concrete [5] as a composite material composed of a mineral aggregate adhering to a binder.

RAP

Recycling of asphalt material is a removable material, in which the total and asphalt exist. It is helping to reduce the ancient materials and preserve the terrestrial space. The pavement material of recycled material is made when the asphalt flooring material is removed from construction or color. Use of rap in road construction [6], through which minimizing waste, maintaining a natural environment, improving performance. Retrieved asphalt flooring (RAP) is garbage material that is produced in the construction process, renewal or demolition of asphalt pavement. Asphalt pavement is usually removed due to the continuous process of rebuilding, reconstruction, and rehabilitation; during the process, the deposit material RAP [7] during these processes is added to many valuable reusable materials such as asphalt binder, bitumen and. RAP is a granular base or base material in almost all sidewalks, with fixed and non-stop roads, road parking, bike trails, gravel roads rehabilitation, Shoulders, Residential Driveways, ditch Fill, Engineering Filling, Pipe Sewage bed, and filling.

Fig.1 : Recycle pavement sample used during experiments

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

METHODOLOGY

The Methodology which is adopted in this paper is an overall study of literature on RAP [8] and used RAP with mixes of aggregates as per IRC grading with some percentage. The test on RAP is done to ensure the durability of RAP to use in a bituminous aggregate. The bitumen is used in testing is of VG-30 grade. Marshal test is performed with different percentages and made a comparison of different results.

This methodology deals with the experimental work done in this thesis that involves mainly two processes that are to say

- Preparation of Marshall samples
- Sample testing

The concepts of the Marshall method of designing bituminous mixtures were first introduced by Bruce Marshall, a former Bituminous Engineer in the Mississippi State Highway Department. It is a design methodology that is adopted worldwide for determining the strength and flow characteristics of the bituminous paving mixes. It is generally used for the design of bituminous mixes which can carry heavy traffic loads by fulfilling the requirements of the pavement surface characteristics. In India, this method is usually preferred to characterize the bituminous mixes and used to calculate the Optimum Binder Content (OBC) for different mixes. Before the study is performed in a laboratory, the density, the tensile strength, and the softening point of bitumen is measured and after that optimum binder's content is found out which is further used in the experiment.

Preparation of Marshall samples

The Marshall method, like other mix design methods, uses several trial aggregate-asphalt binder blends, each with different asphalt binder content. The aggregates and filler are mixed together in the desired proportion to fulfill the design requirements and the specified gradation. For casting the Marshall Sample, 1200 grams of aggregates are taken and mixed with corresponding bitumen content by weight of mix and 0.3% fiber by weight of mix at a mixing temperature of about 160°C. The mixing of aggregates and bitumen should be done properly so that all aggregates are uniformly coated with bitumen. The Marshall mould, collar, and the hammer are preheated in the oven.

The binder should be heated to a temperature of 120°C – 165°C. The weighed quantity of heated bitumen is added to the heated aggregate and the mixture is thoroughly mixed at the specified mixing temperature. The recommended mixing temperature for the VG-30 grade of bitumen is about 160°C.

Required device:

- Moulds
- extracting samples
- pedestriars of compaction and hammer
- thermometers
- water bath
- furnace
- heater
- weighing balance

The Marshall Method of mixing design has two main features.

- Vacuum density analysis
- Stability rate test

The martial stability of the mixture is defined as the maximum load made by a compact sample at a standard temperature of 60°C. The value of the flow is the maximum load on which the martial sample produces a deflection of 0.25 mm during loading. In this method, an attempt is carried to get the optimum binder material for the accumulated mixture type and the intensity of the traffic process:

- Coarse aggregates, finished aggregates and mineral filler ratio should be mixed and so that the final mixture of the mixture should be graduated in the specified range.
- Around 1200 grams aggregates and filling are collected from one degree to 175°C to 195°C.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

- Condensation mould assembly and rammer are cleaned and the temperature from 100°C to 145°C is maintained. Then Bitumen which is in the beaker heated at a temperature of 121°C to 138°C and then the first trial of bitumen test percentage added to the total warm and mixed well with a hand mixer.
- Then, the mixture of all ingredients are heated till the temperature reaches 154°C to 160°C and then the mixture is added to a preheated mould and compacted, made 75 shots on both sides of the sample.
- The weight of the composite taken for sample preparation can be appropriately modified to achieve compact thickness as per standard.
- More than two samples are made on each bitumen percentage.
- The specific gravity of fillers and bitumen Engineering is determined first. The theoretical specific density of the mixture is determined.

Fig.2: Marshall Test in progress

CONCLUSION

1. Normal VG-30 grade of bitumen is tested for different percentages for bituminous concrete mixes and Optimum Binder Content (OBC) is calculated. The OBC for the bituminous concrete comes out to be 5.33 % by weight of mix and the flow value is well within the specified limits as per MoRTH.
2. Bituminous concrete mix having RAP shows better stability as per specified limits as per MoRTH, where Bituminous concrete mix with RAP percentage shows the maximum stability of 2444kg than all other BC mixes.
3. The Bituminous concrete mix with RAP percentage shows the maximum marshal quotient of 734.80kg/mm than all other BC mixes.
4. It is preferable to use RAP of 15% with a specific aggregate gradation with the best bitumen content is 5.33%.
5. It is recommended to carry out an economical visibility study to use RAP with different percentage and it is recommended to carry out different test on other percentage of aggregate up to 60%.

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International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

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